

Laparoscopic repair of inguinal hernia (TAPP) vs open inguinal hernia repair

Authors:

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Inguinal hernia repair is one of the most commonly performed surgical procedures worldwide. Open Lichtenstein repair and laparoscopic transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) repair are widely used techniques for the management of inguinal hernia. This study aimed to compare the outcomes of laparoscopic TAPP repair with open Lichtenstein repair. **Methods:** This prospective interventional comparative study was conducted at the General Surgery Departments of Benghazi Medical Center and Aljala Hospital, Libya, from January 2019 to May 2025. A total of 225 patients with inguinal hernia were included and divided into two groups: Group I included 98 patients who underwent open Lichtenstein repair, while Group II included 127 patients who underwent laparoscopic TAPP repair. All patients underwent complete clinical evaluation, laboratory investigations, and postoperative follow-up for three months. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 30. **Results:** The mean operative time was longer in the TAPP group (116.4 ± 2.8 minutes) compared to the open repair group (62.7 ± 9.9 minutes). The duration of hospital stay was slightly shorter in the TAPP group. Postoperative complications including pain, hematoma, seroma, and wound infection were more common after open repair. Patient satisfaction was higher in the TAPP group (85%) compared to the open repair group (60%). **Conclusion:** Laparoscopic TAPP repair showed fewer postoperative complications, shorter hospital stay, and higher patient satisfaction compared to open Lichtenstein repair, although operative time was longer. TAPP is a safe and effective alternative when performed by experienced surgeons.

Keywords: *Inguinal Hernia; Laparoscopic TAPP; Lichtenstein Repair; Hernioplasty; Postoperative Complications.*

INTRODUCTION:

Notably, correction of inguinal hernias is a common procedure performed by surgeons. Over 800,000 repairs are made annually. An inguinal hernia is a hole in the myofascial plain of the oblique and transversalis muscles that allows intraabdominal or extraperitoneal organs to herniate. These groin hernias can be categorized as femoral, direct, or indirect, depending on their location (Baldini et al., 2024).

Most patients present with groin pain or a protrusion. To avoid complications, medical professionals recommend correcting any symptomatic hernias. An open or laparoscopic procedure can be used to achieve the goal of a tension-free repair and defect closure. The most popular

technique for a tension-free repair is a mesh; if mesh is not suitable, primary suture repair can be performed (Shakil et al., 2020).

There are two types of inguinal hernias: acquired and congenital. Acquired hernias are the most common in adults. There is evidence, though, that suggests genetics also play a part. Inguinal hernias are at least four times more common in people with a known family history of the condition than in those without one (Patel et al., 2021).

Furthermore, studies have shown that several conditions, such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), Ehlers-Danlos syndrome, and Marfan syndrome, increase the risk of inguinal hernias. Additionally, it is believed

that obesity, hard lifting, chronic coughing, and straining from constipation all lead to increased intra-abdominal pressure, which can cause an inguinal hernia (O'Brien et al., 2021).

Aim of the study:

To achieve the optimal management of patients with inguinal hernia.

Objectives of the study:

To make a comparison between laparoscopic and open (Lichtenstein) inguinal hernia repair.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

Study Setting:

This study was conducted at the General Surgery Departments of Benghazi Medical Center (BMC) and Aljala Hospital, Benghazi, Libya.

Study Design:

This prospective interventional comparative study was conducted between January 2019 and May 2025.

Study Population:

Patients diagnosed with inguinal hernia who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled in the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients presenting with inguinal hernia.
- Both male and female patients.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients who refused to participate in the study.
- Patients with congenital anomalies.
- Patients with chronic hepatic or renal diseases.
- Patients who developed major intraoperative complications.

RESULTS:

Demographic Characteristics:

Table (1): Age distribution of the study population.

*Qualitative data are represented as frequencies and relative percentages.

Age (years)	Cases (n=225)	Percentage
20-30	36	16%
31-45	63	28%
46-60	81	36%
61-85	45	20%
Total	225	100%

Sample Size:

A total of 225 patients were included in the study and divided into two groups:

- Group I (n=98): Open Lichtenstein repair.
- Group II (n=127): Laparoscopic TAPP repair.

Preoperative Assessment:

All patients underwent:

- Complete history taking.
- Full general and abdominal examination.
- Routine laboratory investigations including complete blood count, fasting blood glucose, renal function tests, and serum electrolytes.
- Electrocardiography (ECG).
- Chest X-ray.
- Abdominal and pelvic ultrasonography.

Surgical Procedure:

Patients underwent either laparoscopic TAPP repair or open Lichtenstein inguinal hernia repair according to the planned surgical approach.

Follow-up:

Patients were followed for three months postoperatively to assess complications and patient satisfaction.

Ethical Approval:

Approval was obtained from the Research Ethical Committee and Institutional Review Board (IRB). The study was conducted according to the Declaration of Helsinki for studies involving human participants.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 30. Continuous variables were expressed as mean ± standard deviation, while categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Statistical significance was considered at p<0.05

Figure (1): Age distribution of the study population.

225 participants were included in our study. 16% of them were between 20-30 years old, 28% of them were between 31-45 years old, 36% of them were between 46-60 years old and 20% of participants were between 61-85 years old.

Table (2): Sex distribution of the study population.

Gender	Cases (n=100)	Percentage
Male	151	67%
Female	74	33%
Total	225	100%

*Qualitative data are represented as frequencies and relative percentages.

Figure (2): Sex distribution of the study population.

As shown in table (2) and figure (2), 67% participants of our study were males and 33% were females.

Table (3): Analysis of history

Medical history	Number	Percentage
Diabetes	99	44%
Hypertension	54	24%
Past surgeries	18	8%
Others	27	12%
None	27	12%
Total	225	100%

of past medical participants.

*Qualitative data are represented as frequencies and relative percentages.

Figure (3): Analysis of past medical history of laparoscopic TAPP group.

Regarding table (3) and figure (3) and according to the analysis of past medical history we found 44% of patients were diabetic, 24% were hypertensive, 8% had made past surgeries, 12% with other medical history and 12% of patients were without medical history.

Table (4): Distribution of operative data among participants (operative time - hospital stay length).

	Lichtenstein open repair (n = 98)	Laparoscopic TAPP (n = 127)
Operative time (minutes) (mean ± SD)	62.7 ± 9.9	116.4 ± 2.8
Duration of hospital stay (days) (mean ± SD)	1.23 ± 0.58	1.07 ± 0.35

The operative time (minutes) (mean \pm SD) was 62.7 ± 9.9 in Group (1) and 116.4 ± 2.8 in Group (2) while the duration of hospital stay (days) (mean \pm SD) was 1.23 ± 0.58 in Group (1) and 1.07 ± 0.35 in Group (2).

Table (5): Analysis of Post-operative complications.

Post-operative complications	Lichtenstein open repair (n = 98)	Laparoscopic TAPP (n =127)
Pain	39	24
Seroma	5	2
Hematoma	19	10
Infection	8	4
None	27	87
Total	98	127

*Qualitative data are represented as number and frequencies.

As shown in table (5) and figures (4, 5), we found that Lichtenstein open repair patients have more post-operative complications than Laparoscopic TAPP patients.

Figure (4): Analysis of Post-operative complications in Lichtenstein Open repair group (n = 98).

Figure (5): Analysis of Post-operative complications in Laparoscopic TAPP group (n = 127).

Table (6): Analysis of postoperative patient satisfaction.

Satisfaction	Lichtenstein open repair (n = 98)	Laparoscopic TAPP (n = 127)
Satisfied	59 (60%)	108 (85%)
Not satisfied	39 (40%)	19 (15%)
Total	98	127

*Qualitative data are represented as frequencies and relative percentages.

Figure (6): Analysis of postoperative patient satisfaction of laparoscopic TAPP group.

As shown in table (6) and figure (6), we found that 60% of Lichtenstein open repair patients were satisfied and 40% were not satisfied but 85% of Laparoscopic TAPP patients were satisfied while 15% were not satisfied.

DISCUSSION:

The present prospective comparative study evaluated the outcomes of laparoscopic transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) repair versus open Lichtenstein repair in 225 patients with inguinal hernia. The findings demonstrated that laparoscopic TAPP repair was associated with fewer postoperative complications, shorter hospital stay, and higher patient satisfaction compared with open repair, although operative time was longer in the laparoscopic group.

In the current study, the mean operative time was significantly longer in the TAPP group (116.4 ± 2.8 minutes) compared to the open repair group (62.7 ± 9.9 minutes). This finding is consistent with the study conducted by Salama et al. (2019), who reported prolonged operative duration in laparoscopic repair due to the technical learning curve and the need for intracorporeal suturing. However, Eklund et al. (2007) reported no significant difference in operative time between both techniques after adequate surgical experience was achieved.

The present study also showed that patients who underwent laparoscopic TAPP repair had a shorter duration of hospital stay and fewer postoperative complications including pain, hematoma, seroma, and wound infection. Similar findings were reported by Schmedt et al. (2005) and Haladu et al. (2022), who concluded that laparoscopic repair provides better postoperative recovery with reduced postoperative pain and earlier return to normal activities.

Patient satisfaction was notably higher in the laparoscopic TAPP group (85%) compared with the open repair group (60%). This may be attributed to less postoperative pain, improved cosmetic outcome, and faster recovery following laparoscopic surgery. Previous studies by Salama et al. (2019) and Bittner et al. (2012) also demonstrated improved patient satisfaction and reduced chronic groin pain after laparoscopic hernia repair.

Although laparoscopic TAPP repair showed several advantages, the procedure requires advanced surgical expertise and has a significant learning curve. In addition, previous studies have reported a slightly increased risk of visceral and vascular injuries during laparoscopic procedures compared with open repair (Wake et al., 2005). Therefore, surgeon experience plays an essential role in achieving optimal outcomes.

Overall, the findings of the current study are consistent with previously published literature supporting laparoscopic TAPP repair as a safe and effective alternative to open Lichtenstein repair, particularly in patients requiring rapid postoperative recovery and reduced postoperative discomfort.

LIMITATIONS:

The present study had several limitations. First, it was conducted at two centers within a single geographic region, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Second, the follow-up period was relatively short (three months), limiting long-term assessment of recurrence and chronic postoperative pain. Third, the study lacked randomization, which may introduce selection bias. Finally, the sample size was relatively moderate and larger multicenter randomized studies are recommended for further validation of the findings.

CONCLUSION:

This study concluded that laparoscopic TAPP repair was associated with fewer postoperative complications, shorter hospital stay, and higher patient satisfaction compared to open Lichtenstein repair. Although laparoscopic TAPP required longer operative time and greater surgical expertise, it represents a safe and effective technique for inguinal hernia repair when performed by experienced surgeons.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding:

No financial support was received for this study.

Data Availability:

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Author Contributions:

- Conceptualization: Anis M. Mohamed
- Data Collection: Talal K. Abdelsalam
- Statistical Analysis: Jalal Ali El roey
- Manuscript Drafting: Akram Issa El.Shaikhy
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